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Gamification guideline

UPSKILLS Intellectual output 3.2

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UPSKILLS: UPgrading the SKILLS of Linguistics and Language Students

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About

The definition of gamification is the application of game-design elements and game principles in non-game contexts.

Gamification of education is a developing approach for increasing learners' motivation and engagement by incorporating game design elements in educational environments.

Game elements and principles are the rules and rewards that appear in a program on a digital platform. Examples may include points, levels, missions, leader boards, badges and progress. Game mechanics are how participants engage with a gamification program and receive next steps and feedback on accomplishments.

Gamification – at its core – is about driving engagement to influence learning results.

What is the value of gamification in the class?

Gamification is the strategy for influencing and motivating the behavior of students, which also includes teachers. Gamification can be applied across a broad spectrum of situations where individuals need to be motivated to pursue specific actions or activities. Game elements make a student's job more transparent by making goals clear and easy to follow. A student is able to see progress on performance, receive immediate feedback on accomplishments and connect with colleagues through collaboration and competition.

These guidelines summarise the content available on the UPSKILLS project Moodle platform - <https://upskills.fil.bg.ac.rs/>.

Tiles format

A course format which displays course topics as "Tiles", in a grid rather than as a list. When clicked, tile content is displayed under the tile with an animated transition. The layout adapts to different screen sizes and orientations. Within each tile, activities can also be set to display as "sub-tiles". For each tile, the teacher can pick an icon from a predefined set, or upload a background photo.

*This course has a Tiles format!

- **Tiles** are used to show course topics and activities
- **Animation** is used to expand tiles to reveal content
- **Icons or photos** on each tile increase visual appeal
- **Modal windows** (animated pop ups) to show content
- **Colors** for tiles are customizable
- **Easy to switch** into Tiles from other formats (e.g. Topics, Grid) without changing course content
- **User friendly** (e.g. tile icons are provided and don't need to be uploaded)
- **Mobile responsive** (adapts to different screen sizes and orientations)
- **Progress** shown on tile with % in a circle, or as a fraction

Example:

Instruction:

Go to your course, on the up right side of the course find the icon and go to Edit settings. Find Course format and choose Tile format for your course. There you can choose the color of the icons, progress circle in every tile and subtitles if needed. For every option there is an explanation which can be found in the question mark icon.

Quizzes - step by step

The question bank allows a teacher to create, preview and edit questions in a database and use them in the Quiz or Lesson activity. Questions are organized in categories and subcategories similar to the way files are stored in folders and subfolders.

The question bank offers versioning of questions in order to guarantee transparency and traceability of edits even if several teachers are working on the same questions together. To further facilitate collaboration and organization of questions, questions may be commented on, marked as a draft and tagged.

#How to access the question bank

The question bank is always accessed in the course. It can only be accessed by people having at least the teacher role in the course in question.

The screenshot shows the Moodle course interface for 'Upskills'. The course title is 'Experiential training'. The breadcrumb trail is 'Home / Courses / Experiential training'. The main content area shows a list of topics: 'Announcements', 'Topic 1', 'Topic 2', and 'Topic 3'. On the right side, a settings menu is open, showing options like 'Edit settings', 'Course completion', 'Filters', 'Gradebook setup', 'Backup', 'Restore', 'Import', 'Copy course', 'Reset', 'Accessibility toolkit', and 'More...'. A red arrow points to the 'More...' option.

#Categories

Questions are organized into categories. Initially each course has only one category called "Default". You can create a hierarchy of categories because you can create subcategories inside parent categories. To add or edit categories click on the "Categories" tab.

#Add a new question

The screenshot shows the 'Add a new question' interface. At the top, there are four tabs: 'Questions', 'Categories', 'Import', and 'Export'. The 'Categories' tab is selected. Below the tabs, the heading 'Question bank' is displayed. A dropdown menu labeled 'Select a category:' shows 'Default for Experiential training'. Below this, a note states: 'The default category for questions shared in context 'Experiential training''. There is a section for tag filters with the text 'No tag filters applied' and a 'Filter by tags...' dropdown. Below that are three checkboxes: 'Show question text in the question list' (unchecked), 'Also show questions from subcategories' (checked), and 'Also show old questions' (unchecked). At the bottom, there is a button labeled 'Create a new question ...'.

This is the first step for making a question. You can put it in the default category of the course.

#Question types

Choose a question type to add ✕

QUESTIONS

Select a question type to see its description.

- Multiple choice
- True/False
- Matching
- Short answer
- Numerical
- Essay
- Calculated
- Calculated multichoice
- Calculated simple
- Drag and drop into text
- Drag and drop markers
- Drag and drop onto image
- Embedded answers (Cloze)
- Random short-answer matching
- Select missing words

OTHER

- Description

Add Cancel

#Standard question types

1. Multiple choice

With the Multiple Choice question type you can create single-answer and multiple-answer questions, include pictures, sound or other media in the question and/or answer options (by inserting HTML) and weight individual answers.

2. Short Answer

In response to a question (that may include an image), the respondent types a word or phrase. There may be several possible correct answers, with different grades. Answers may or may not be sensitive to case.

3. Embedded Answers (Cloze Test)

These very flexible questions consist of a passage of text (in Moodle format) that has various answers embedded within it, including multiple choice, short answers and numerical answers.

Questions consist of a passage of text (in Moodle format) that has various sub-questions embedded within it, including:

- short answers (SHORTANSWER or SA or MW), case is unimportant,
- short answers (SHORTANSWER_C or SAC or MWC), case must match,
- numerical answers (NUMERICAL or NM),
- multiple choice (MULTICHOICE or MC), represented as a dropdown menu in-line in the text,
- multiple choice (MULTICHOICE_V or MCV), represented as a vertical column of radio buttons, or
- multiple choice (MULTICHOICE_H or MCH), represented as a horizontal row of radio-buttons,
- multiple choice (MULTIRESPONSE or MR), represented as a vertical row of checkboxes
- multiple choice (MULTIRESPONSE_H or MRH), represented as a horizontal row of checkboxes

The structure of each cloze sub-question is identical:

{ start the cloze sub-question with a bracket

1 define a grade for each cloze by a number (optional). This used for calculation of question grading. Note that this number can only be a positive integer (1, 2, 3, etc.)

:SHORTANSWER: define the type of cloze sub-question. Definition is bounded by ':'.

~ is a separator between answer options

= marks a correct answer

marks the beginning of an (optional) feedback message

} close the cloze sub-question at the end with a bracket

Now a very simple example:

```
{1:SA:=Berlin} is the capital of Germany.
```

More examples:

```
Which animal eats mice? (answer: the cat)
```

```
{1:MC:=the cat~the dog}
```

Quiz Settings in Moodle

#Timing:

By default, learners have unlimited time to pass the exam, we'll set an assessment period and time limit.

The screenshot shows the 'Timing' section of Moodle quiz settings. A red box highlights the 'Open the quiz' and 'Close the quiz' settings. The 'Open the quiz' setting is configured with a duration of 30 minutes, starting on April 11, 2022, at 11:00, and is enabled. The 'Close the quiz' setting is configured with a duration of 30 minutes, starting on April 11, 2022, at 11:30, and is also enabled. The 'Time limit' is set to 0 minutes and is disabled. The 'When time expires' setting is set to 'Open attempts are submitted automatically'.

Opening and closing options are the frame of quiz availability. Time limit is a duration of the quiz, once it started.

The rest of the options in this section can be left as they are by default.

#Grade

Grade

Grade category	<input type="text" value="Uncategorised"/>
Grade to pass	<input type="text"/>
Attempts allowed	<input type="text" value="Unlimited"/>
Grading method	<input type="text" value="Highest grade"/>

Grades will be shown in many steps when making a quiz so it can be done at the end when all questions have been made. The important part here is the option "Attempts allowed", it is the number of attempts which students can do the quiz. If it is more than 1 you can choose the grading method.

#Layout

You can group questions into blocks and place each question on a single page, or all the questions on one page.

Layout

New page	<input type="text" value="Every question"/>
Show less...	
Navigation method	<input type="text" value="Free"/>

Navigation method is an option to choose between free and sequential progress through the quiz. In you choose sequential, student will have to go through the quiz in order and may not return to previous questions.

#Question behaviour

Shuffle within questions will be randomly shuffled each time users take the quiz.

#Review options

There are 4 phases of review:

▼ Review options ?

During the attempt	Immediately after the attempt	Later, while the quiz is still open	After the quiz is closed
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The attempt ?	<input type="checkbox"/> The attempt	<input type="checkbox"/> The attempt	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> The attempt
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Whether correct ?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Whether correct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Whether correct	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Whether correct
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Marks ?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Marks	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Marks	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Marks
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specific feedback ?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specific feedback	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specific feedback	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Specific feedback
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> General feedback ?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> General feedback	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> General feedback	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> General feedback
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Right answer ?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Right answer	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Right answer	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Right answer
<input type="checkbox"/> Overall feedback ?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Overall feedback	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Overall feedback	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Overall feedback

If you uncheck the attempt, students will see only the grade and feedback.

#Safe Exam Browser

Safe Exam Browser is a customized web browser, available for Windows (7, 8.1, 10), macOS (starting 10.7, recommended 10.11 or newer) and iOS (9.3.5 or newer). The application must be downloaded and installed on the device that the student uses to attempt the quiz.

- Students will only be able to attempt the quiz if they are using Safe Exam Browser.
 - The browser window won't have a URL or search field and back/forward navigation and reload can be disabled.
 - Safe Exam Browser cannot be closed until the test is submitted.
 - Switching to other applications is disabled by default, but it's possible to allow to use specific third party applications during an exam.
 - Shortcut keys such as Win+Tab, Alt+Tab, Ctrl+Alt+Del, Alt+F4, Print Screen, Cmd+Tab are disabled or cannot be used to close Safe Exam Browser or to switch to other user accounts on the computer. The possibility of taking screen shots is disabled.
 - The clipboard is cleared when starting and quitting Safe Exam Browser.
 - The browser context menu is disabled.
 - Specific web sites/pages/resources can be configured to be accessible during an exam, using a URL filter.
 - Spell checking and dictionary lookup is disabled, but can optionally be allowed.
- The link for download is [here](#).

#Overall feedback

Overall feedback is an optional text shown after the quiz attempt. You can choose the percentage in which you will write the feedback.

Badges

Badges are a good way of celebrating achievement and showing progress. Badges may be awarded based on a variety of chosen criteria and may be displayed on a user's profile

There are two categories of badges:

- Site badges - available to users site-wide and related to the site wide activities, like finishing a set of courses.
- Course badges - available to users enrolled in the course and related to the activities that happen inside the course.

Adding/Managing Badges

Go to your course to the setting option:

The screenshot shows a Moodle course page for 'Experiential training'. The breadcrumb trail is 'Home / My courses / Experiential training'. The page content includes an 'Announcements' section and four 'Topic' sections (Topic 1, Topic 2, Topic 3, Topic 4). In the top right corner, there is a user profile for 'Nada Soldatic' and a notification 'You are logged in as Jelena Gledic'. A settings gear icon is visible in the top right corner of the course page. A red arrow points to the 'More...' option in the settings dropdown menu, which is open and shows options: 'Edit settings', 'Course completion', 'Filters', 'Gradebook setup', 'Backup', 'Restore', 'Import', 'Reset', 'Recycle bin', and 'More...'.

You can add or manage the existing badge:

Badges

[Manage badges](#)
[Add a new badge](#)

Adding a new badge you will give the name, description and upload the badge in the right format.

Once uploaded, you have to set the criteria for the badge:

- Manual issued by the role of the user
- When the course/module is completed
- Activity completion (set up of 1+ activities done before the set deadline)

Badge example

[Home](#) / [Courses](#) / [Gamification guideline](#) / [Badges](#) / [Manage badges](#) / [Badge example](#)

Badge example

Criteria for this badge have not been set up yet.

[Overview](#) [Edit details](#) [Criteria](#) [Message](#) [Recipients \(0\)](#) [Endorsement](#) [Related badges \(0\)](#) [Alignments \(0\)](#)

Add badge criteria

To start adding criteria, please select one of the options from the drop-down menu.

Level up!

- Level up! is a customizable block which a teacher can add to a course to give experience points to students as they progress through a course.
- It displays their current level and progress towards the next level.

Instructions:

- With the editing turned on in a course, select Level up! from the 'Add block' menu.
- Access the block on the course page and click the configuration icon.
- Give the block a title and description and save it again.
- Click the links in the block to access different areas:
 - **Information** - shows how many points are required for each level. You can change this from the Levels tab.
 - **Ladder** - shows the students in order of levels and experience points
 - **Report** - allows for filtering the students, levels and experience point and allows for manual editing of students' experience points via their progress bar.
 - **Settings** -allows various options to be turned on or off and offers settings for preventing possible cheating.

Set up the experience points:

- Once the block is added, if you don't do anything, by default, certain course actions will count towards experience points. You can change this.
- From the **Rules** tab, click *Add rule* and then decide how many points and if you want all or any of the conditions to apply:

Course rules

Info Ladder Report Log Levels **Rules** Visuals Settings ★ Plus

Did you know that with *Level up! Plus* students can receive points for *completing courses and activities, c*

Events rules ?

+ Add a rule

+ 5 points are earned when: 🗑️

ANY of the conditions are true ⌵

+ Add a condition

+ Add a rule

Save changes Cancel

When you are adding a condition, you can choose the following condition types:

The screenshot shows the 'Course rules' interface with a modal titled 'Pick a condition type'. The modal lists four options:

- Specific event**: Choose the action that users must perform out of a curated list of events.
- Activity or resource**: This condition requires that the action takes place in a specific activity or resource.
- Event property**: This condition is for power users with a technical understanding of the events and their properties.
- Set of conditions**: Combine multiple conditions into one.

- As students progress throughout the course and take part in activities, they gain more points and these are related to a set of levels.
- The teacher can decide the number of points to levels in the *Levels* tab and students can view this from the **Information** link.
- Students can see their progress by clicking the *Ladder* link:

The screenshot shows the 'Ladder' interface with a table of student progress:

Rank	Level	Participant	Total	Progress
1	3	Tanja Samardžić	45 ⁰⁰	<div style="width: 19%;"></div> 19 ⁰⁰ to go
2	3	Test 1	40 ⁰⁰	<div style="width: 24%;"></div> 24 ⁰⁰ to go
3	2	Maja Miličević Petrović	30 ⁰⁰	<div style="width: 7%;"></div> 7 ⁰⁰ to go

They can view their level and progress in the block itself, and when they move up a level, they are notified (if enabled by the teacher from the *Settings* tab.)

Stashes

Stash is a block that allows a teacher to create and then show items around a course. Students can then go and collect these items which will then appear in their stash block. The stash block is a good way to encourage more interaction with activities and is invaluable for teachers looking to gamify their course.

Instructions:

- Click on the settings link in the stash block.
- Click on the "Add an item" button to add an item.
- Both a name and an image must be supplied.
- Clicking "Save and next" will progress to a location page.

Items

Items Trade Report

Add new location

What's this? A location is a place where you intend to display your item.

▼ General

Item example

Location

Supplies Unlimited

Collection interval

Save and next Save changes Cancel

There are required fields in this form marked .

Location is the field for you so you will know where is the stash. One item has the ability to be located in many different places. Each location determines how many times a student can collect an item from that area. You can also set the time limit for the pick up.

The next step is to choose the appearance of the stash:

Items

Items Trade Report

Snippet for 'in the page'

What's next? Once you have created the item and the location, you need to add a code snippet to your course for the item to be displayed. After customising how the item will be displayed to your students, copy the snippet below and paste it in your content, in the description of an assignment for instance.

Appearance

Snippet

`[stashdrop secret="OJaXEm" image]`

Copy and paste this into an editor in different activities around your course.

Back to the main screen

Now you can select (and copy) all the content of the Snippet box, which you will later paste into the Atto editor inside an activity. In that way you will put stashes in your activities wherever you want.

Resources and activities

Resources

A resource is an item that a teacher can use to support learning, such as a file or link. Moodle supports a range of resource types which teachers can add to their courses. In edit mode, a teacher can add resources via the 'Add an activity or resource' link. Resources appear as a single link with an icon in front of it that represents the type of resource.

- Book - Multi-page resources with a book-like format.
- File - A picture, a pdf document, a spreadsheet, a sound file, a video file
- Folder - For helping organize files and one folder may contain other folders
- Label - Can be a few displayed words or an image used to separate resources and activities in a topic section, or can be a lengthy description or instructions
- Page - The student sees a single, scrollable screen
- URL - You can send the student to any place they can reach on their web browser

Activities

An activity is a general name for a group of features in a Moodle course. Usually an activity is something that a student will do that interacts with other students and or the teacher.

- Assignments - Enable teachers to grade and give comments on uploaded files and assignments created on and off line
- Chat - Allows participants to have a real-time synchronous discussion
- Choice - A teacher asks a question and specifies a choice of multiple responses
- Feedback - For creating and conducting surveys to collect feedback
- Forum - Allows participants to have asynchronous discussions
- Glossary - Enables participants to create and maintain a list of definitions, like a dictionary
- Lesson - For delivering content in flexible ways
- Quiz - Allows the teacher to design and set quiz tests, which may be automatically marked and feedback and/or to correct answers shown

Lessons

The Lesson activity allows teachers to create 'branching' exercises where students are presented with content and then, depending on their responses, are directed to specific pages. The content may be text or multimedia.

How to set up?

- In a course, with the editing turned on, choose 'Lesson' from the activity chooser.
- Give it a name and, if required, a description.
- Expand the other sections to select the settings you want, including whether the Lesson is for practice or will be graded.
- Click Save and Display and from the Edit tab, add your first page. This will usually be a Content page (where you add information) or a Question page (where you can select a question type.)
- Make sure the 'Jumps' take you to the next page (if you want.) 'Jumps' direct the student to where they should go next. Once you have made all your pages, return and edit each Jump so it shows the correct page name.

Glossary

The Glossary activity allows participants to create and maintain a list of definitions, like a dictionary. While it can be set up and used only by the teacher, its main function is as a collaborative exercise. The Glossary auto-linking filter will highlight any word in the course which is located in the Glossary.

How to set up?

- In a course, with the editing turned on, choose 'Glossary' from the activity chooser.
- Give it a name and, if required, a description.
- Expand the other sections to sections to define the settings you want, in particular:
 1. Entries - decide if you want to allow editing of entries, duplicate entries, unmoderated entries etc
 2. Appearance - decide how you want the Glossary to be displayed. This affects the browsing options for students.
- Click Save and display

#Entries

Approved by default

If set to "yes" then new entries appear automatically. If not, then the teacher must approve each one first.

Always allow editing

If set to "yes", students can edit their entries at any time. If not, then they can only edit for a certain period.

Duplicate entries allowed

This allows the entry of more than one definition for a given word.

Allow comments on entries

Students and teachers can leave comments on glossary definitions. The comments are available through a link at the bottom of the definition.

#Appearance

Display format

This specifies the way that each entry will be shown within the glossary. The default formats are:

- Simple, dictionary style - This looks like a conventional dictionary with separate entries. No authors are displayed and attachments are shown as links.
- Continuous without author - Like the simple style. Shows the entries one after other without any kind of separation but the editing icons, but only if your theme supports it, you usually have to modify the theme if you want an alternative appearance to the simple setting.
- Full with author - A forum-like display format showing author's data. Attachments are shown as links.
- Full without author - A forum-like display format that does not show author's data. Attachments are shown as links.
- Encyclopedia - Like 'Full with author' but attached images are shown inline.
- Entry list - This lists the concepts as links.

Course completion

Course completion shows if a course has been completed. It can show the progress a student is making towards finishing the course according to specific criteria. The criteria can include meeting an activity's grade level or a manual checking "complete" by either the student and/or teacher.

Instructions:

Course completion can be found in the general settings of your course (up in the right corner).

Condition: Date

If you tick the Enable box you can then set a date after which the course will be declared complete.

Condition: Enrolment duration

If you tick the Enable box you can then choose a number of days after enrolment upon which the course will be marked complete.

Condition: Unenrolment

If you tick "Enable" here then the course will be marked complete once the student is unenrolled.

Condition: Course grade

If you tick the Enable box, you can set a passing grade for the course. Please note that course grade in Completion status is looking at total of points rather than a percentage.

Condition: Manual self-completion

If this is enabled then a student can mark the activities complete themselves.

ALL means that each role must mark the course complete before; ANY means that it will be classed as complete once one role has marked it complete.